

RELEVANCE OF SWAMI VIVEKANANDA'S THOUGHTS IN TODAY'S PERSPECTIVE

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Impact of Music in Vivekananda's Life

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Music is the highest art and, to those who understand is the highest worship.

-Swami Vivekananda

Vishnu, one of three supreme gods of Hinduism, told Narada Nahamtisthami Baikunthe, Yoginamhridayenacha. Matbhaktahyatrageyanti, tatrasthami Naradah.

(I do not reside in the Heavenly abode of Baikuntha, nor in the heart of the Yogis. Where ever my devotees sing in spirit, I reside there, Narada)

Music plays a big role in transforming Narendra Nath in to Swami Vivekananda. Swami Vivekananda believes that high achievements in art, music, etc., are the results of concentration. When we hear beautiful music, our minds become fastened upon it, and we cannot take them away. Those who concentrate their minds upon what you call classical music do not like common music, and vice versa. Music in which the notes follow each other in rapid succession holds the mind readily. A child loves lively music, because the rapidity of the notes gives the mind no chance to wander. A man who likes common music dislikes classical music, because it is more complicated and requires a greater degree of concentration to follow it. He think that, if there are different musical instruments tuned alike in one room, all of you may have noticed that when one is struck, the others have the tendency to vibrate so as to give the

same note. So all minds that have the same tension, so to say, will be equally affected by the same thought Swami Vivekananda himself was a trained singer (though not professional). He received his classical music training from BeniOstad. In his first meeting (late 1881) with Ramakrishna, he sang few devotional songs. His trained voice and his devotion towards music highly impressed Ramakrishna, which was followed by a cordial invitation to visit Dakshineswar. We find Ramakrishna repeatedly requesting Narendra to sing and while listening to Narendra's song Ramakrishna is going into trance (Ramakrishna Kathamitra). Vivekananda was undoubtedly an appreciator and a performer of classical music. In 1887, when Vivekananda was only 24 years old, he co-edited and published a Bengali song anthology named SangeetKalpataru. He believes that drama and music are by themselves religion; any song, love song or any song, never mind; if one's whole soul is in that song, he attains salvation, just by that; nothing else he has to do; if a man's whole soul is in that, his soul gets salvation. They say it leads to the same goal.

In music, nobody, not even the sage Bharata, the originator of dramatic performances, could understand whether it was singing, or weeping, or wrangling, and what meaning or purpose it sought to convey! And what an abundance of intricacies in that music! What labyrinths of flourishes enough to strain all one's nerves! Over and above that, that music had its birth in the nasal tone uttered through the teeth compressed, in imitation of the Mohammedan musical experts! Nowadays there is an indication of correcting these; now will people gradually understand that a language, or art, or music that expresses no meaning and is lifeless is of no good. Now they will understand that the more

strength is infused into the national life, the more will language art, and music, etc. become spontaneously instinct with ideas and life. The volume of meaning that a couple of words of everyday use will convey, you may search in vain in two thousand set epithets. Then every image of the Deity will inspire devotion, every girl decked in ornaments will appear to be a goddess and every house and room and furniture will be animated with the vibration of life.

In India, music was developed to the full seven notes, even to half and quarter notes, ages ago. India led in music. India gave to the world her system of notation, with the seven cardinal notes and the diatonic scale, all of which we enjoyed as early as 350 B.C., while it came to Europe only in the eleventh century.

While discussing the preparations one needs to take to practise Bhakti Yoga, Vivekananda told that the greatest aid to this practice of keeping God in memory is, perhaps, music. The Lord says to Nârada, the great teacher of Bhakti, "I do not live in heaven, nor do I live in the heart of the Yogi, but where My devotees sing My praise, there am I". Music has such tremendous power over the human mind; it brings it to concentration in a moment. You will find the dull, ignorant, low, brute-like human beings, who never steady their mind for a moment at other times, when they hear attractive music, immediately become charmed and concentrated. Even the minds of animals, such as dogs, lions, cats, and serpents, become charmed with music. Shankaracharya had caught the rhythm of the Vedas, the national cadence. Indeed I always imagine that he had some vision such as mine when he was young, and recovered the ancient music that way. Anyway, his whole life's work is nothing but that, the throbbing of the beauty of

the Vedas and the Upanishads.

The book SangeetKalpataru is all in us. Fool, hearest not thou? In thine own heart day and night is singing that Eternal Music-Sachchidânanda, soham, soham-Existence-Knowledge-Bliss Absolute, I am He, I am He. All poetry, painting, and music is feeling expressed through words, through colour, through sound. Music is the highest art and, to those who understand is the highest worship.

It is clear that Vivekananda's musical mind-set plays a big impact on his life. His thoughts, thinking, vision and prospective towards life and humanity is highly influenced by his musical heart and brain.

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